

What is self-deceit?

Victoria Derewońko

Student, IX Liceum Ogólnokształcące z Oddziałami Dwujęzycznymi
im. Św. Królowej Jadwigi w Rzeszowie, Poland

June 2025

Introduction

Self-deceit is a complex process, described as *seeing the world the way we wish it to be rather than the way it is* (*Self-Deception*, n.d.). In psychology, it is commonly understood as a coping mechanism for uncomfortable truths, known to be rooted in cognitive and biological processes. The essence of self-deceit can be captured in Oscar Wilde's *De Profundis: Man is least himself when he talks in his own person. Give him a mask, and he will tell you the truth.* (Wilde, 1905) – the first and most natural human reflex is to lie to themselves.

Self-deceit is often viewed as an unconscious mechanism, a result of distorted thinking (Freud, 1936). However, alternative theories suggest it is a deliberate decision of self-delusion (Festinger, 1957). And so, the fundamental question becomes: Is self-deceit a conscious (deliberate) or an unconscious (automatic, intuitive) process? To address this matter, we must inspect the factors and indications of self-deceit. By exploring these, this essay aims to determine the nature of self-deceit.

Psychoanalytic psychology

Imagine an ordinary morning in a well-kept home. Knock - at the door stands a police officer. They explain that the son had been involved in an accident - alcohol abuse. Parents declare: *There must be a mistake.* No evidence can convince them.

The father thinks: *He's not like that. I raised him well.*

Freud introduces and operates on the ego - the foundation of individuals' self-worth, the mediator between the id and the superego. *The poor ego... serves three harsh masters and does what it can to bring their claims and demands into harmony with one another.* (Freud, 1923) - this illustrates that when faced with damaging self-image facts, the ego may resort to defence mechanisms to protect individuals.

In the above case, boys' parents engage in denial - *a defense mechanism in which unpleasant thoughts, feelings, wishes, or events are ignored or excluded from conscious awareness* (APA Dictionary of Psychology, 2018). That happens unconsciously, to preserve self-worth and identity as exemplary parents.

Whilst Freud highlights unconscious mechanisms, alternative viewpoints argue that individuals may deliberately avoid distressing information - self-deceit themselves. Baumeister and Newman (1994) state that humans may engage in strategic ignorance - avoiding certain truths. However, that does not imply conscious self-deceit. Thus, neuroscientific research highlights that even these decisions are primed by unconscious processing which can introduce biased perception before consciousness is able to intervene (Da Klerk, 2017), and they gradually become one of unconscious defences. These findings reinforce the thesis of self-deceit as an unconscious defense mechanism.

Lauria et al. (2016) suggest that self-deceit plays a role in maintaining emotional stability by encouraging more pleasant interpretations of the situation. In our example, embarking on their sons' identity would require parents to face negative feelings - guilt, disappointment, and long-term relationship rupture. They resort to denial - an adaptive response. This, *ipso facto*, aligns with emotional psychology studies and emotion regulation strategies (Gross & Thompson, 2007). Taylor and Brown (1988) present self-deceit as sustaining emotional health through maintaining protective illusions, e.g., an obedient son. In the above situation, by self-deceiving themselves, parents save emotional connection with their son, instinctively protecting the stability of the family.

Cognitive psychology

Widely known, Kahneman's theory presents a model of thinking, distinguishing between: System 1 – fast and emotional – and System 2 – slow and logical (Kahneman, 2011). In charged emotional situations, System 1 is likely to dominate, leading individuals to overlook or distort facts. For our characters, news about their son collides with their mental schemas, threatening their worldview. This triggers the emotional response – an unconscious use of System 1 - heuristics and confirmation biases, aimed at dismissing evidence and causing self-deceit (Tversky and Kahneman, 1974).

An American philosopher, Alfred Mele (2001), provides a model of self-deceit divided into “straight” - protective; and “twisted” – self-sabotaging – categories. He argues that certain self-deceiving behaviours involve cognitive manipulation (e.g., reinterpretation), presenting described processes as semi-conscious. However, empirical studies show that even in these cases an individual's reasoning and actions are *de facto* motivated by automatic mechanisms: emotions or desires. For instance, in Hart et al. (2009) participants unconsciously showed selective processing - analysing negative evidence less critically when it aligned with their beliefs. This discloses how involuntary affective attachment can disrupt cognition, reinforcing self-deceptive thinking.

Another layer of critique relies on motivated reasoning theory - individuals model their thinking to reach desirable conclusions. It appears in Kunda (1990) - people are more critical of facts contrary to their beliefs than the ones supporting it. Extending this, it seems that even deliberate thinking is compromised by bias – intrusive feelings and developed reflexes, as humans unconsciously organise perception and cognition to make certain deductions seem true. Following this, motivated reasoning theory actually promotes the view of self-deceit as an unconscious mechanism.

When parents face a reality contrasting with their previous beliefs, arising discomfort may lead to unconsciously rejecting or distorting reality – reducing the mental strain and preserving well-being. This process is called cognitive dissonance, *deriving from individuals' discomfort out of holding contrasting cognitions, triggering them to reduce inconsistency and restore mental equilibrium* (Festinger, 1957). Parents telling themselves the police have made a mistake proceed to align their beliefs towards rationalising altered situations.

In philosophy the concept of self-deceit is a recurring theme, presented as an individual's consistent process of lying to themselves to escape responsibility – e.g., Sartre's (1956/1943). Although this offers an interesting perspective, researchers suggest that consistent and self-preserving lies are far more likely to emerge through unconscious processes, with cognitive dissonance or identity threats involved (Gilbert, 2006) - *de facto* tethering self-deceit to intrusive copying mechanisms.

Social psychology

From then on parents hear murmurs: *We thought they were such a respectable family...* When the mother passes by, the air feels heavier. At home, she looks at the diplomas on the wall. She ignores the whispers, reminding herself: *The boy the police spoke of couldn't be my son - the son of the bank chairwoman. We are not the kind of parents people could talk about like that.*

Social roles are *a socially defined pattern of behavior that is expected of a person who occupies a certain social position or belongs to a particular social category* (Shackelford & Weekes-Shackelford, 2021), e.g., a good parent. They are an important part of an identity and society. They're ever-present, inhibiting or commanding our actions. A meta-analysis by Aberson, Healy & Romero (2000) depicts how grave is their impact on us - individuals strongly identifying with their groups show significantly higher levels of bias in interpreting morally ambiguous situations, in favour of their ingroup. Crucially, these biases are not an effect of deliberate action but rather a variation in how individuals perceive and interpret situations. This stands in line with the Social Identity Theory - postulating that membership in a group is a part of one's identity and carries great emotional significance (Tajfel and Turner, 1986) - and supports the idea that self-deceit can become an intuitive process, protecting individuals from identity-threatening information.

In light of the above facts, the parents' refusal to accept the evidence can be interpreted as a necessity to protect their identity and social roles, fulfilling their responsibilities as socially defined parental roles.

Moreover, it is widely known that human beings are social organisms with a need for group affiliation and interpersonal connections. Since the age of stone, humans have been aware that group membership is essential for survival, leading them to invest effort and be ready to take a risk as a means to gain acceptance and become a member of the group. Numerous studies and real-life situations indicate that people may behave deceptively, irrationally or unethically in order to remain a part of and benefit the community - as an unconscious way of preserving their own safety and identity.

One example of that action is parents' self-deceit against evidence. Confronted with the exclusion from the society, they experience ethical fading - allowing them to ignore or rationalise their son's activities in the name of the group's interest (Tenbrunsel & Messick,

2004). Their actions are influenced by fear and shame. This cognitive mechanism is clearly shown by the mother's internal monologue and implies an automatically created rationalisation, driven by self-deceit.

Although it is established that our personality is shaped by social roles, some may argue that individuals consciously arrange their actions to uphold these roles. For example, the parents' approach in the story could be, *prima facie*, interpreted as intentionally forging their attitude to defend their status. Nonetheless, research indicates that social and cultural norms are so deeply internalised that the necessity to maintain them becomes an automatic psychological response. What could look like a premeditated social deception is *de facto* a conditioned reflex, guided by psychological regulation (Greenwald & Banaji, 1995). Continuing this line of reasoning, the above information is in favour of describing self-deceit as an unconscious process, shaped by cultural and societal influences.

Biological and neurological psychology

It became the routine to wander around the house. The TV played a news report flashing photos from the crime scene - with their son on them. Yet father whispered: *To make such a mistake...* When neighbours started asking questions, mother answered with a polite smile: *You must be thinking of somebody else.* They ignored the lack of calls. *He is busy with his responsibilities* - they said.

We should not disregard the role that physiological factors of our body have on our thinking process and actions. Neuroscience supports the thesis that self-deceit is rooted in brain biology and activity. For instance, Antonio Damasio (1994) posits that emotional memory and somatic markers play a crucial role in emotionally charged situations, helping individuals to avoid mental harm through intuitive filtering awareness - acting as if psychological action posed a real-life threat. MRI scans have enabled us to find the neural pathways conditioning described mechanisms - heightened activation in the ventromedial prefrontal cortex (emotional evaluation) and decreased activation in the dorsolateral prefrontal cortex (rational thinking), which draws a causation that emotional overwhelming may trigger belief distortion and cloud scrutiny of thinking (Berlin, 2011).

Another contributing factor is degeneration or impairment of executive functions - *cognitive processes that are necessary for purposeful, future-oriented behavior* (Welsh et al., 2008) - elaborated in Zelazo and Cunningham (2007). In conclusion, "hot" executive functions (under psychological stress) limit our ability to think rationally: reevaluate assumptions or create opinions (Zelazo, 2015), allowing for unconscious self-deception. Throughout story the boy's parents are placed under sudden and overwhelming emotional pressure, which most likely impairs their executive functioning, leading them to involuntary self-deceit.

Evolutionary psychology presents the theory that self-deception may be an evolutionary adaptation for the purpose of effectively deceiving others - due to the fact that individuals

believing in their own lies are less likely to reveal deception. Robert Trivers (2000) implies a strategic role of self-deceit as a tool for enhancing survival, attributing to it both conscious and unconscious elements. At the same time, it is rational to conclude that the majority of self-deception is an unconscious procedure, generally because it increases its usefulness - as our system suppresses uncomfortable truths before they transpire to consciousness, the deceiver appears more credible. Von Hippel and Trivers (2011) reinforce that idea through studies exhibiting reduced physiological leakage and an increase in trustworthiness when attendees were unaware of self-deception. Ergo, even if self-deceit is perceived as an adaptation, its execution remains biologically regulated, optimised for unconscious processing.

Conclusion

Throughout this essay we described and analysed theories from various branches of psychology. During that, it becomes evident that when individuals encounter facts threatening their identity, mental stability or safety, the mind instinctively uses self-deceit as a defense. The parents in our narrative are not deliberately choosing blindness or manipulation, but rather are unconsciously shielded by evolved psychological mechanisms prioritising survival over reality – biology and chemistry of body. Self-deceit is a natural, human response to psychological threat - unconscious act of self-preservation and final defense against unbearable truths.

Acknowledgments

I would like to express my sincere gratitude to my psychology teacher, Anna Brzezińska, M.A., for her valuable insight while drafting this essay and reviewing its earlier version.

Bibliography:

Aberson, C. L., Healy, M., & Romero, V. (2000). Ingroup bias and self-esteem: A meta-analysis. *Personality and Social Psychology Review*, 4(2), 157–173.

https://doi.org/10.1207/s15327957pspr0402_04

Baumeister, R. F., & Newman, L. S. (1994). Self-Regulation of cognitive inference and decision processes. *Personality and Social Psychology Bulletin*, 20(1), 3–19.

<https://doi.org/10.1177/0146167294201001>

Berlin, H. A. (2011). The neural basis of the dynamic unconscious. *Neuropsychoanalysis*, 13(1), 5–31. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15294145.2011.10773654>

Damasio, A. R. (1994). *Descartes' Error: Emotion, Reason, and the Human Brain*. Putnam.

Retrieved 2025 from: <https://philpapers.org/rec/DAMDEE>

De Klerk, J. J. (2016). Nobody is as Blind as Those Who Cannot Bear to See: Psychoanalytic Perspectives on the Management of Emotions and Moral Blindness. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 141(4), 745–761. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-016-3114-x>

Festinger, L. (1957). *A Theory of Cognitive Dissonance*. Stanford University Press.

Freud, A. (1936). *The Ego and the Mechanisms of Defense*.

Freud, A. (1937). *The Ego and the Mechanisms of Defence*. Karnac Books. Retrieved 2025 from: <https://psptraining.com/wp-content/uploads/Freud-A.-1936-1993.The-ego-and-the-mechanisms-of-defence.-London-Karnac-Books.pdf>

Gilbert, D. T. (2006). *Stumbling on Happiness*. Knopf.

Greenwald, A. G., & Banaji, M. R. (1995). Implicit social cognition: Attitudes, self-esteem, and stereotypes. *Psychological Review*, 102(1), 4–27. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0033-295x.102.1.4>

Gross, J. J., & Thompson, R. A. (2007). Emotion Regulation: Conceptual Foundations. In J. J. Gross (Ed.), *Handbook of emotion regulation* (pp. 3–24). The Guilford Press.

Hart, W., Albarracín, D., Eagly, A. H., Brechan, I., Lindberg, M. J., & Merrill, L. (2009). Feeling validated versus being correct: A meta-analysis of selective exposure to information. *Psychological Bulletin*, 135(4), 555–588. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0015701>

Kahneman, D. (2011). *Thinking, Fast and Slow*. Farrar, Straus and Giroux.

Kunda, Z. (1990). The case for motivated reasoning. *Psychological Bulletin*, 108(3), 480–498. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0033-2909.108.3.480>

Lauria, F., Preissmann, D., & Clément, F. (2016). Self-deception as affective coping. An empirical perspective on philosophical issues. *Consciousness and Cognition*, *41*, 119–134. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.concog.2016.02.001>

Mele, A. R. (2001). *Self-Deception Unmasked*. Princeton University Press.

Sartre, J.-P. (1956). *Being and Nothingness* (H. Barnes, Trans.). Methuen. (Original work published 1943)

Self-Deception. (n.d.). *Oxford Bibliographies*. <https://www.oxfordbibliographies.com/display/document/obo-9780199828340/obo-9780199828340-0067.xml>

Shackelford, T. K., & Weekes-Shackelford, V. A. (2021). *Encyclopedia of Evolutionary Psychological Science*. Springer.

Tajfel, H., & Turner, J. (1986). The Social Identity Theory of Intergroup Behavior. Retrieved 2025 from: <https://www.christosaioannou.com/Tajfel%20and%20Turner%201986.pdf>

Taylor, S. E., & Brown, J. D. (1988). Illusion and well-being: A social psychological perspective on mental health. *Psychological Bulletin*, *103*(2), 193–210. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0033-2909.103.2.193>

Tenbrunsel, A. E., & Messick, D. M. (2004). Ethical Fading: The Role of Self-Deception in Unethical Behavior. *Social Justice Research*, *17*(2), 223–236. <https://doi.org/10.1023/b:sore.0000027411.35832.53>

Trivers, R. (2000). The elements of a scientific theory of self-deception. *Annals of the New York Academy of Sciences*, *907*(1), 114–131. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1749-6632.2000.tb06619.x>

Tversky, A., & Kahneman, D. (1974). Judgment under uncertainty: Heuristics and biases. *Science*, *185*(4157), 1124–1131. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.185.4157.1124>

Von Hippel, W., & Trivers, R. (2011). The evolution and psychology of self-deception. *Behavioral and Brain Sciences*, *34*(1), 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.1017/s0140525x10001354>

Welsh, M. C., Friedman, S. L., & Spieker, S. J. (2008). Executive Functions in Developing Children: Current conceptualizations and questions for the future. In *Blackwell Publishing Ltd eBooks* (pp. 167–187). <https://doi.org/10.1002/9780470757703.ch9>

Wilde, O. (1905). *De Profundis*. Retrieved 2025 from: <https://www.gutenberg.org/ebooks/5170>

Zelazo, P. D. (2015). Executive function: Reflection, iterative reprocessing, complexity, and the developing brain. *Developmental Review*, *38*, 55–68. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dr.2015.07.001>

Zelazo, P. D., & Cunningham, W. A. (2007). Executive Function: Mechanisms Underlying Emotion Regulation. In J. J. Gross (Ed.), *Handbook of emotion regulation* (pp. 135–158). The Guilford Press.

